

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN THE BUYING INTENTION OF FASHION PRODUCTS

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Abstract

People in the twenty-first century do not have the time to visit and engage with one another. Through social media, users may join to social networking sites and stay in touch even when they are far away. In addition, social media platforms like Facebook foster a devoted relationship between the fashionable product and the consumer also helps in influencing customers for buying motive, opening up significant advertising prospects. Similar to this, other social media platforms, such as blogs, offer a place for people to comment on events that require publicising and can be used as a marketing tool for both customer adoption and promotions of fashion industry. People are now finding your social media page for buying by following and subscribing to fashionable pages and blogs. Since there is a lag between the time a social event occurs and when it is transmitted, these media have an advantage over other widely used public media, such as television. This study focuses on the tactics that can expand the current viral marketing model outside the realm of traditional social media. Consequently, it can aid in forging a strong enough community to support initiative buying and efficient marketing.

Keywords: Fashionable, Fashion Industry, Time, Social Media, Buying Intention.

INTRODUCTION

Social networking has become a social media trend setter in the current digital era as individuals spend more and more time online. These days, social media platforms rank among the most effective marketing strategies for fashion companies and serve as the main information source for consumers. Instagram, for instance, is thought to be the most significant source of fashion intelligence. The fashion sector has profited from leveraging social media to draw customers and raise brand awareness. They have posted images and videos and written articles regarding their clothing and accessories and company practices. Social media, in particular, offers fashion firms an engaging mass communication tool to enhance their marketing approach. By providing knowledge on fashion and brands, these platforms draw in new customers and retain existing ones by providing fresh avenues for advertising.

Fashion companies still have difficulties when utilising internet marketing in social media spaces, even though they produce and distribute value-added content there to meet the demands and wishes of their customers. Consumers want fashion brands to engage with them in real time by being active on social media and fostering emotional bonds. Fashion brands may view digital advertising as more authentic, valuable, and effective than traditional advertising, given the immense capacity of generating content and capturing customers' attention on social media. Given how quickly the advertising industry is changing, this may be the best course of action

for taking charge and getting the desired outcomes. The goal of the Journal of Engaging Advertising is to "advancing our understanding of interacting marketing, advertisement, and conversation in a networked world." In light of the fashion industry's expansion and the latest advancements in digital while social technologies, it is crucial to comprehend how interactive advertising affects consumer behaviour in the fashion industry.

Significance of the study

The motive of the study is to show the Impact of social media marketing and its influence towards purchasing behaviour for fashion products.

Statement of the problem

Prices in Social media are low compared to offline retail shops, Offers and discounts are more, New and latest trend can be obtained easily, Convenient to use social media especially for fashionable attires, User friendly platform, Reviews based platform by which defaults or damages' are reduced, Various westernized fashions can be explored at one place, Worth for money, Always product Availability is there, Trendy collections can be purchased firstly, Convenient way of exploration, 24/7 access to products, Installment facilities can be availed, Full information about the product can be known before purchase itself, Mode of purchasing is very easy and comfortable the main work as these many perceptions has been viewed in this study.

Objective of the study

To study the Impact of social media marketing and its influence towards buying intention of fashion products.

Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant difference between Impact of social media marketing and Age of the respondents in fashion products.

H02: There is no significant difference between buying intention of fashion products and Gender of the respondents.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The process of enumeration, as well as the correct recording of outcomes, is referred as data collection. The proper data is critical to the success of an investigation; the study comprises assessing the respondent's Commitment influence in various aspects, as well as the researcher employ the current study was carried out in a practical world situation.

Sample Design

The approaches of random samples were used to get the main data. Questionnaire was used to perform a field survey. The employees participating in the trial is using a straightforward convince sampling technique, with 250 as sample size.

Statistical Tools

The ANOVA, Descriptive, and Simple percentage analysis has been used to analyze the connection towards Influence on buying pattern and social media advertising towards fashion industry.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Erdoğan (2012), for a very long time, one of the key topics of marketing study has been creating and sustaining brand loyalty. Marketers have employed diverse strategies to uphold their clients' brand loyalty. Social media marketing is one of the more modern strategies. Given that the idea is gaining more traction in marketing academics and among professional marketers, the purpose of this study is to determine how social media marketing affects customer brand loyalty. The study, which employed the SPSS 17.0 edition, demonstrated that customer brand loyalty is positively impacted when a brand uses favourable marketing, delivers relevant material, offers popular content, appears on several platforms, and offers social media applications.

Zulqurnain (2016), The rapidly expanding use of social media technologies offers a variety of fresh approaches to product marketing. Social media and the internet have now become indispensable to a business's expansion, and this technology has changed how people do business. It is imperative that every company use this technology to promote their goods. In this study, we evaluate how social media marketing affects consumers' perceptions of products and their decision to purchase them. We evaluate the effectiveness of door-to-door and promotion marketing in conjunction with social media marketing.

Jayasuriya (2017) Given Facebook's enormous global popularity, the goal of this study was to determine which Facebook marketing initiatives affect brand equity and to evaluate the relative contributions of each initiative to the development of brand equity. This essay reviews the research on social media marketing, focusing especially on Facebook marketing features and how they relate to brand equity. Even though social media is widely used, sufficient study on the connection between marketing via social media and brand equity has only recently been conducted. However, the lack of empirical findings further contributes to the paucity of available data in this field. There is very little study on identifying the relationship amongst FM and BE in the context of the Asia-Pacific area. In a corporate setting, this study integrates social media theory and brand management literature. By doing thus, this study contributes to the body of information regarding the connection between marketing on Facebook and customer loyalty by providing a new, theoretically grounded structured model.

Rienda (2021), Research examines how social media presence and trademark development affect international operations and how they affect performance in small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in the UK and Ireland who operate in the fashion industry. Information from multiple data sources was integrated to perform quantitative analysis. Using variance-based mathematical modelling of structural equations (partial least squares) and vicariate analysis, the research model's hypotheses are tested on a representative group of 102 SMEs. This

research aims to explore the impact of trademark as social media engagement on businesses, which varies according on the priorities set by management of small and medium-sized fashion enterprises. Therefore, depending on their companies' goals and strategy, managers may find either of these marketing tools helpful in determining how much money to invest in registering a trademark or maintaining a social media presence.

Dewi (2022), The goal of the study is to comprehend how social media marketing affects brand awareness, which in turn affects consumers' propensity to make purchases in the fashion sector. The three variables—social advertising, intent to purchase, and brand awareness—are examined using a qualitative methodology. 270 respondents are required as samples for this study, and SPSS is used to process the data for validity, reliability, normalcy, classic presumption, single, then multiple linear regression analysis. The Sobel Test also makes use of SPSS results. The hypothesis is evaluated and supplemented with secondary evidence from literature investigations. Every hypothesis has considerable positive influences based on the test results. In conclusion, social media marketing can have a big impact on a brand's intention to buy. This influences customers' purchase intentions by raising brand awareness

Demographic Profile:

Table 1: Age of the Respondents

S. No	Age of the Respondents	No. of respondents
1	10or 25 years	75
2	26-40 years	100
3	41-55 years	50
4	Above 55 years	25
Total		250

Source: Primary Data

The table 1 shows that the most of the respondents (100) belong to the age category of 26 to 40 Years, followed by 75 respondents belong to 10 to 25 Years category, followed by 50 and 25belong to 41 to 55 Years and above 55 Years respectively.

Table 2: Gender of the Respondents

S. No	Age of the Respondents	No. of respondents
1	Female	124
2	Male	126
Total		250

Source: Primary Data

Table 2shows that it can be noted that out of total respondents 250 investigated in the study in that 124 in Females, followed by males with 126 respondents.

Table 3: Impact of Social Media Marketing

S. No.	Sources	Always	Usually	Occasionally	Not Usually	Never	Total
1	The prices in Social media are low compared to offline retail shops.	72	100	40	30	8	250
		28	40	16	13	3	100.00
2	Offers and discounts are more.	50	45	38	89	30	250
		20	18	15	35	12	100.00
3	New and latest trend can be obtained easily.	65	50	91	31	13	250
		26	20	37	12	5	100.00
4	Convenient to use social media especially for fashionable attires.	115	40	40	35	20	250
		41	15	17	14	8	100.00
5	User friendly platform	80	45	43	51	31	250
		33	18	17	20	12	100.00
6	Reviews based platform by which defaults or damages' are reduced.	93	74	48	20	15	250
		38	29	19	8	6	100.00
7	Various westernized fashions can be explored at one place.	89	56	38	27	40	250
		35	24	15	10	16	100.00
8	Worth for money	100	43	11	58	38	250
		39	17	6	23	15	100.00
9	Always product Availability is there.	76	60	40	38	36	250
		30	25	16	15	14	100.00
10	Mode of purchasing is very easy and comfortable.	120	32	20	58	20	250
		47	14	8	23	8	100.00

Sources: Primary Data

Demographic variables and Impact of social media marketing

$H_0 3a$: There is no significant different between employee demographic variables and job.

ANOVA Test of Age and Impact of Social media marketing

Table 4: Age and Impact of Social Media Marketing

Variables	Age	N	Mean	S.D.	F Value	Sig.
The prices in Social media are low compared to offline retail shops.	10or 25 years	75	3.21	0.86	2.890	0.045*
	26-40 years	100	4.36	0.75		
	41-55 years	50	3.21	1.02		
	Above 55 years	25	4.02	1.20		
	Total	250	4.25	0.99		
Offers and discounts are more.	10or 25 years	75	4.22	0.87	3.596	0.018*
	26-40 years	100	4.19	0.93		
	41-55 years	50	3.89	1.00		
	Above 55 years	25	4.15	0.94		
	Total	250	4.11	0.98		
New and latest trend can be obtained easily.	10or 25 years	75	3.94	0.71	4.360	0.006*
	26-40 years	100	4.06	0.90		
	41-55 years	50	3.74	1.15		
	Above 55 years	25	3.77	1.17		
	Total	250	3.94	1.00		
Convenient to use social media especially	10or 25 years	75	4.26	0.98	4.077	0.007*

for fashionable attires.	26-40 years	100	3.84	1.04		
	41-55 years	50	3.90	1.44		
	Above 55 years	25	3.67	1.08		
	Total	250	3.89	1.15		
User friendly platform	10or 25 years	75	4.29	0.76	5.068	0.001*
	26-40 years	100	3.74	1.58		
	41-55 years	50	3.81	1.75		
	Above 55 years	25	3.78	1.33		
	Total	250	3.84	1.12		
Reviews based platform by which defaults or damages' are reduced.	10or 25 years	75	4.47	0.70	4.046	0.003*
	26-40 years	100	4.37	1.00		
	41-55 years	50	4.39	0.82		
	Above 55 years	25	4.95	0.89		
	Total	250	4.23	0.91		
Various westernized fashions can be explored at one place.	10or 25 years	75	3.77	0.90	3.258	0.027*
	26-40 years	100	4.09	0.82		
	41-55 years	50	4.05	1.02		
	Above 55 years	25	4.32	0.82		
	Total	250	4.10	0.89		
Worth for money	10or 25 years	75	3.46	0.84	2.710	0.049*
	26-40 years	100	3.67	1.06		
	41-55 years	50	4.15	0.97		
	Above 55 years	25	3.85	1.04		
	Total	250	3.95	1.01		
Always product Availability is there.	10or 25 years	75	4.01	1.06	3.369	0.025*
	26-40 years	100	3.09	1.00		
	41-55 years	50	4.30	0.93		
	Above 55 years	25	4.21	0.86		
	Total	250	4.10	0.98		
Mode of purchasing is very easy and comfortable.	10or 25 years	75	4.42	0.96	6.963	0.001*
	26-40 years	100	3.06	1.30		
	41-55 years	50	4.07	1.11		
	Above 55 years	25	3.97	1.18		
	Total	250	3.87	1.21		

Based on Primary Data * Sig.@5%

The ANOVA test results of age and -variables are significant at 5% level. Hence, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. User friendly platform with the mean of 3.84, Various westernized fashions can be explored at one place with F value of 3.258, Mode of purchasing is very easy and comfortable as the mean is 3.87, Reviews based platform by which defaults or damages' are reduced as the F value is 4.046, The prices in Social media are low compared to offline retail shops as the mean is 4.25, Offers and discounts are more as the mean is 4.11 and the F value is 3.596 and New and latest trend can be obtained easily as the F value is 4.360 and mean is 3.94.

Table 5: Intention of Fashionable Products Buying through Social Media

S. No.	Sources	Always	Usually	Occasionally	Not Usually	Never	Total
1	Trendy collections can be purchased firstly.	65	50	91	31	13	250
		26	20	37	12	5	100.00
2	Convenient way of exploitation	89	56	38	27	40	250
		35	24	15	10	16	100.00
3	24/7 access to products	120	32	20	58	20	250
		47	14	8	23	8	100.00
4	Installment facilities can be availed	72	100	40	30	8	250
		28	40	16	13	3	100.00
5	Full information about the product can be known before purchase itself.	115	40	40	35	20	250
		41	15	17	14	8	100.00

Sources: Primary Data

T Test of Gender and buying intention of fashionable products

H_0 3b: There is no significant different between employee demographic variables and job.

Table 6: Gender and Buying Intention of fashionable products

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	T Value	Sig.
Trendy collections can be purchased firstly.	Male	126	4.22	1.00	9.701	0.001*
	Female	124	4.92	0.28		
	total	250	4.36	1.39		
Convenient way of exploitation	Male	126	4.09	0.99	3.621	0.025*
	Female	124	4.54	0.72		
	total	250	4.69	0.89		
24/7 access to products	Male	126	3.91	1.01	4.590	0.007*
	Female	124	4.50	0.66		
	total	250	3.69	1.08		
Installment facilities can be availed	Male	126	3.87	1.14	3.690	0.029*
	Female	124	4.42	1.14		
	total	250	4.86	1.02		
Full information about the product can be known before purchase itself.	Male	126	3.81	1.12	6.890	0.001*
	Female	124	4.58	0.72		
	total	250	4.42	0.97		

Based on Primary Data * Sig.@5%

The T- test results of age and -variables are significant at 5% level. Hence, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. Trendy collections can be purchased firstly as the mean is 4.36, Convenient way of exploration as the T value is 3.621, 24/7 access to products with the mean score of 3.69 and T value is 4.590, Installment facilities can be availed as the mean is 4.86 and T value is 3.690 and Full information about the product can be known before purchase itself the mean is 4.42 and the T value is 6.890.

Findings of the study

1. The study shows Reviews based platform by which defaults or damages' are reduced as the F value is 4.046.
2. The study finds that 24/7 access to products with the mean score of 3.69 and T value is 4.590.
3. The study concluded User friendly platform with the mean of 3.84.
4. The study finds that Offers and discounts are more as the mean is 4.11 and the F value is 3.596.

Suggestions of the study

1. Social media is nor good nor bad does it depend upon the user and using patterns.
2. The social media marketing influence the customers towards the new and fashionable items through creating fake trends and irrespective fashion not considering the geographical area and traditional culture.
3. The social media platforms are high in spreading various cultural habits but making us to forget our own culture and fashion.
4. In the name of fashion the traditional believes and respect decreases, for that the new corporate can concentrate more on traditional fashion comeback items by which traditional heritage can be preserved and making it fashionable to latest trends also.

CONCLUSION

The fashion industry's use of social media marketing to draw in customers. It synchronizes purchase commitment, brand attachment, brand preference, brand loyalty, and social media marketing of fashion businesses and influencers.

We discovered that customers have a strong emotional connection to the online activities they engage in, and that they also hold a strong positive perception of local fashion brands.

We found that preference for a brand is equally significant. Customers have predetermined tastes due to the high caliber of fashion products, and they communicate with businesses through social media marketing. It was discovered that the consumers exhibited very little brand identification and loyalty.

The statistical insignificance of these elements was verified by the regression equation. Brand attachment and preference were important, but brand loyalty was minimal, indicating a lack of commitment to a purchase.

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